

II SOUTHERN SCIENCE CONFERENCE

2024 - VIRTUAL CONFERENCE AND IN PERSON EDITION

AN INTERACTIVE CHEMISTRY GAME FOR EDUCATIONAL ENGAGEMENT

DE BONI, Luis Alcides Brandini^{1*}; HASSAN, Saif Al-Deen Hasan ²; RASHEED, Ali Abulridha³

¹ Araucária Scientific Association, Chair office, Brazil.

²Department Business Administrator, College of Administration and Economics, University of Misan, Maysan, Iraq.

³ Electronic Computing Center, University of Misan, Maysan, Iraq.

* Correspondence author
e-mail: labdeboni@gmail.com

Received 02 Agosto 2024; received in revised form 02 October 2024; accepted 13 October 2024

ABSTRACT

This project aimed to develop an interactive chemistry game accessible on mobile devices and computers to make learning basic chemistry concepts more engaging for students. The game was created using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, ensuring cross-platform compatibility. Initial tests showed that the game successfully captured students' interest with its intuitive interface and appealing design. While the game proved attractive to young students and encouraged exploration of chemical concepts in a playful manner, areas for improvement were identified, including expanding educational content and providing more detailed user feedback. The game's flexibility in access and positive reception by test users highlight its potential as an educational tool for teaching chemistry. With further enhancements, this game could become a valuable resource in chemistry education, leveraging widespread mobile device usage to transform these devices into productive learning tools.

Keywords: *Interactive Learning, Chemistry Education, Mobile Gaming, Educational Technology, Game-Based Learning.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This project, born from a family initiative to create educational tools, explores the potential of educational games in learning. Authors like Vieira (2016), Tupin, Borges, and Duarte (2021), Lima & Mesquita (2008), Silva, Nogueira, & Souza (2012), and De Souza and Rua (2010) have demonstrated the educational value of such games in promoting engagement and understanding complex concepts.

While mobile phones as educational tools have limitations, Hamari *et al.* (2016) note that challenging games can enhance learning through engagement. When used appropriately, mobile devices can transform screen time into productive educational experiences.

Research by Wouters *et al.* (2013) and Connolly *et al.* (2012) provides evidence of the

positive cognitive and motivational effects of serious games across various disciplines. Sung and Hwang (2013) and Tsai & Tsai (2020) further support the effectiveness of game-based learning in science and chemistry education.

This project aims to develop an interactive game to assist in chemistry education, offering a resource that both entertains and educates, inspiring students to explore new concepts engagingly.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Computer:
Model: Intel Core i7
Operating System: Windows 11
Code Editor: Sothink HTML Editor

Artificial Intelligence Resources:
 ChatGPT: Used to generate and correct code by leveraging pattern analysis in existing code.
 Google Gemini: Employed to generate and refine code and provide insights and suggestions.
 Perplexity AI: Utilized to generate code snippets and offer real-time coding assistance.
 Claude AI: Applied to generate, correct, and optimize code through advanced machine learning techniques.

2.2. Methods

The game implements a column correlation system for inorganic chemical compounds, matching formulas with names. This method was chosen to aid memorization and understanding of chemical formulas while promoting interactive learning.

Developed using HTML for structure, CSS for styling, and JavaScript for functionality, the game ensures accessibility, visual appeal, and interactivity. JavaScript enables column correlation, instant feedback, and learning reinforcement.

Initial testing was conducted to ensure smooth functionality across mobile devices and computers. The integration of modern technologies and agile practices, along with AI assistance for code generation and correction, resulted in a timely, robust educational tool meeting established objectives.

2.2.1. Game description

a) Splash Screen (figure 1): The game opens with a language selection screen, enhancing accessibility and providing a personalized experience for diverse users.

Programa Educacional Araucária Associação Científica

Exercícios de Química.

Escolha seu idioma / Choose your language:

Figure 1. Language selection screen.

b) Avatar Creation Screen (Figure 2): Players can create a customized avatar, enhancing engagement and fostering a deeper connection with the game.

Figure 2. Avatar selection screen

c) Column Matching Game Screen (Figure 3): The main gameplay features a column-matching system for various chemical functions (acids, bases, salts, oxides, or mixed). This allows players to focus on specific areas or challenge themselves with broader topics.

Figure 3. Column correlation game.

c.1) Auditory and written feedback reinforces learning by indicating correct and incorrect matches.

c.2) A scoreboard tracks correct matches, adding competition and motivation.

c.3) Players can start a new game or select a different chemical function upon completion.

These features create an engaging, educational experience supporting chemistry learning through interactivity and immediate feedback. To have a simple game experience, please visit: <https://acaria.org/codes/code14.htm>.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The game works well on Firefox across devices, ensuring wide accessibility. Testers appreciated the intuitive interface, engaging design, avatar customization, and immediate feedback. The language selection (English/Portuguese) and scoreboard function correctly, broadening the game's reach and motivating players. Avatar creation, though simple, enhances engagement. These results suggest the game effectively meets its objectives as an engaging educational tool for chemistry, suitable for various educational settings.

Improvements needed:

- Enhance mobile interface for better user experience
- Implement result-sharing feature to boost engagement and competition
- Add timer to scoreboard to evaluate and challenge response times
- Include the avatar into the game

These enhancements would increase accessibility, user engagement, and game complexity.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The developed code created a simple game reinforcing basic chemical concepts (acids, salts, bases, oxides) by associating formulas with compound names. This interactive format enhances memorization and engagement, making learning more accessible. The game's success suggests it can be a valuable complementary tool in chemistry education.

5. DECLARATIONS

5.1. Acknowledgments

The author thanks his daughter for the motivation to make the mobile phone an

increasingly useful tool in education.

5.2. Open Access

This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. Suppose material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license, and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use. In that case, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

6. REFERENCES

- Vieira, L. M. (2016). *Uso dos jogos didáticos como instrumento metodológico*. Retrieved from <https://repositorio.ufpe.br/bitstream/123456789/39605/1/VIEIRA,%20Luciana%20M%20unique.pdf>
- Chaves Saúde Tupin, J., Borges, C. W., & Carlos Duarte, E. (2021, July 15). JOGO DIDÁTICO INVESTIGATIVO COMO INSTRUMENTO DE ENSINO E DESENVOLVIMENTO DA ARGUMENTAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA. *Revista Ciências & Ideias* ISSN: 2176-1477. Instituto Federal de Educacao Ciencia e Tecnologia do Rio de Janeiro - IFRJ. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.22407/2176-1477/2021.v12i2.1481>
- Tsai, C.-Y., & Tsai, C.-C. (2020). Game-based learning has good chemistry with chemistry education: A three-level meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching**, 57(8), 1083-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21765>
- Hamari, J., Shernoff, D. J., Rowe, E., Coller, B., Asbell-Clarke, J., & Edwards, T. (2016). Challenging games help students learn: An empirical study on engagement, flow, and immersion in game-based learning. *Computers in Human Behavior*,

- 54, 170-179.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.07.045>
5. Sung, H.-Y., & Hwang, G.-J. (2013). A collaborative game-based learning approach to improving students' learning performance in science courses. *Computers & Education*, 63, 43-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.11.019>
 6. Wouters, P., van Nimwegen, C., van Oostendorp, H., & van der Spek, E. D. (2013). A meta-analysis of the cognitive and motivational effects of serious games. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(2), 249-265. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031311>
 7. Connolly, T. M., Boyle, E. A., MacArthur, E., Hainey, T., & Boyle, J. M. (2012). A systematic literature review of empirical evidence on computer games and serious games. *Computers & Education*, 59(2), 661-686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.03.004>
 8. Meyerovich, L. A., & Rabkin, A. S. (2013). Empirical analysis of programming language adoption. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 48(10), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2544173.2509515>
 9. Crockford, D. (2008). *JavaScript: The Good Parts*. O'Reilly Media.
 10. LIMA, T. da C., & MESQUITA, N. A. da S. (2008, August 20). APPROACHES TO CHEMICAL TOPICS IN THE MEDIA AND THEIR POSSIBLE INTERACTIONS IN THE CLASSROOM. *Periódico Tchê Química*. Dr. D. Scientific Consulting. Retrieved from http://dx.doi.org/10.52571/PTQ.v5.n10.2008.AGOSTO/2_pgs_14_20.pdf
 11. SILVA, C. K. O., NOGUEIRA, J. P. A., & SOUZA, H. Y. S. (2012, January 20). APPLICATION OF A EDUCATIONAL GAME AS RESOURCE FOR TEACHING CHEMISTRY. *Periódico Tchê Química*. Dr. D. Scientific Consulting. Retrieved from http://dx.doi.org/10.52571/PTQ.v9.n17.2011.6_Periodico17_pgs_6_16.pdf
 12. DE SOUZA, P. S. A., & RUA, E. R. (2010, August 20). GUANABARA BAY: ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION THROUGH AN INTERDISCIPLINARY THEMATIC. *Periódico Tchê Química*. Dr. D. Scientific Consulting. Retrieved from http://dx.doi.org/10.52571/PTQ.v7.n14.2010.24_Periodico14_pgs_23_29.pdf